

D1.1 - Management and Quality Control Plan

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Deliverable Abstract

Plan to ensure high-quality management activities (e.g., deliverables quality control; reporting; KPIs, risks management; internal communication)

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QUALITY CONTROL

Date	Name	Organisation
Reviewer 1:	Leaders of WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	UU; INGV; CNRS; ORB
Reviewer 2:	-	-

TERMINOLOGY

Acronym	Definition
AB	Advisory Board
DoA	Description of Action
ECO	Executive Coordinator Office
KoM	Kick off Meeting
NACB	National Authorities Consultation Board
OEB	Optimization and Evolution Board
WP	Work Package
PC	Project Council
SCC	Service Coordination Committee

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Executive summary

D1.1 outlines the strategies for maintaining high-quality management activities within the EPOS ON project. It details the procedures for effective oversight, including deliverable quality control, reporting protocols, KPIs, risk management, and internal communication. By establishing clear guidelines for these processes, this document serves as a comprehensive resource for EPOS ON beneficiaries, ensuring consistent quality standards and effective project management throughout all phases of the project.

Introduction

WP1 is designed to ensure the successful, seamless, and high-quality management of the project, covering both contractual and financial aspects, as well as operational and strategic oversight (Task 1.1). It also ensures efficient project governance and internal communication (Task 1.2), effective risk management and impact assessment (Task 1.3), and the optimal dissemination and exploitation of the project's results and achievements, including communication efforts to promote the project throughout its lifespan (Task 1.4). Additionally, WP1 coordinates closely with WP6 to maximize the exploitation of project outcomes by EPOS ERIC.

This Deliverable presents the management and quality control plan for the EPOS ON project. It outlines the procedures adopted to guarantee the consistent quality of EPOS ON outcomes. In particular, the following aspects are addressed:

- Composition, roles, decision-making processes, and responsibilities of the EPOS ON management and governing bodies;
- Identification of the quality control procedures necessary to ensure the effective, smooth, and high-quality management of the project, including the risk management;
- Monitoring of the workflow and performance through appropriate indicators;
- Adoption of suitable tools to ensure effective internal communication and maximize the exploitation of project outcomes.

1. EPOS ON Management Structure

The management structure of the EPOS ON projects has been designed to guarantee the appropriate level of quality of the contractual, ethical, financial and administrative organisation of the project. It is described in the Grant Agreement (WP1 and section 3.2) and formalised in the Consortium Agreement. Each project Beneficiary has specific roles and in general, it should fulfil its tasks duly, timely and according to the distribution of work specified in the Description of Action (DoA).

The following project roles are defined:

The EPOS ON project coordinator acts as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

In particular, the coordinator is responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under this Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement;
- keeping the address list of members of the Consortium Bodies and other contact persons updated and available;
- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certification) and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority;
- preparing the meetings, proposing decisions and preparing the agenda of the Project Council meetings, chairing the meetings when the coordinator assumes the role of Chair, preparing the minutes of the meetings and monitoring the implementation of decisions taken at meetings;
- transmitting promptly documents and information connected with the Project to any other Party concerned;
- administering the EU financial contribution of the Granting Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks;
- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims.

If one or more of the Parties is late in submission of any Project deliverable, the coordinator may nevertheless submit the other Parties' Project deliverables and all other documents required by the Grant Agreement to the Granting Authority in time.

The EPOS ERIC Executive Coordination Office (ECO) assists the project coordinator in managing the Project.

The **Work Package Leader** is responsible for managing and coordinating all tasks within the work package, ensuring they align with the project's objectives outlined in the DoA. The WP Leader provides strategic guidance and reports progress to the Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB) and the Project Council (PC).

The **Task Leader** has a hands-on role in managing the execution of the specific task. They ensure that the task outcomes meet quality standards and comply with project requirements by closely monitoring the work of

each participant involved in the task, reporting any risks or issues that may arise, and directly reporting to the WP Leader.

The Governance of the EPOS ON project is made up of a governing body, the **Project Council (PC)**, an executive body, the **Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB)**, a consultation board, the **National Authorities Consultation Board (NACB)** and an advisory body, the **Advisory Board (AB)**. The ECO provides the secretariat to the PC, OEB, NACB, and AB.

1.1 Project Council (PC)

Project Council (PC) is the decision-making body of the EPOS ON Project. It is composed by one representative for each Party, and it is chaired by the coordinator, as decided by the PC. The PC supervises the project workplan on a high level and is the body having the authority to alter the work plan to any significant degree if necessary. It maintains an overview of the EPOS ON project deciding on issues related to the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

The Project Council consists of one representative of each Party. Each Party will name a member for the PC. The coordinator chairs all meetings of the PC as decided during the kick-off meeting in Rome, on October 2, 2024.

The PC shall be free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions in accordance with the procedures set out herein.

Each PC Member shall be deemed to be duly authorised by the Party he/she is representing to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters related to content, finances and intellectual property rights, evolution of the consortium, breach, defaulting party status and litigation.

1.2 Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB)

Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB) is composed by the Work Package Leaders and by the coordinator acting as the Chair. The OEB will monitor and assess the project activities to effectively reach project results. The OEB is responsible to empower the project coordinator to inform the PC, the ultimate decision body, about any significant deviation in the project activities and to provide solutions and proposals as part of the risk management. The OEB interacts with the EPOS ERIC Service Coordination Committee to reflect on strategies and recommendations for the optimization and evolution of the EPOS Research Infrastructure.

The OEB is responsible for:

- keeping track of the effective and efficient implementation of the Project, based on the DoA, particularly regarding the completion of the work package activities in tasks and deliverables of each Party;
- evaluating suggestions of the Work Package Leaders for the reallocation of tasks in work packages;

- making suggestions for amendments to Annex 1 and Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement to the Project Council, especially if restructuring is required to reach the Project's objectives or in case of termination of a Party;
- assessing the status or completion of the activities within each work package and preparing the periodic reporting for the work packages together with the coordinator;
- supporting the coordinator in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in preparing related information and deliverables;
- supporting the coordinator in the collection of information regarding the termination report and amendment procedures in case of termination of a Party's participation;
- suggesting performance indicators for the determination of proper implementation of work package activities to the Project Council.
- providing solutions and proposals as part of the risk management for any significant deviations in the project activities and empowering the project coordinator to inform the PC.

1.3 National Authorities Consultation Board (NACB)

The **National Authorities Consultation Board (NACB)** is made up of governmental representatives from those countries involved in the EPOS Research Infrastructure but not ERIC Members yet. The NACB is a consultation board in which national authorities can follow the EPOS progress to increase their interest in EPOS and find information and documents necessary to start the national process to join EPOS ERIC. Information flow to NACB will be ensured by the WP6 in synergy with the WP1. The NACB Chair will be appointed by the NACB members.

1.4 Advisory Board (AB)

The Advisory Board (AB) is composed of experts, not engaged in EPOS, such as research infrastructure managers; internationally recognized scientists; e-science experts; managers from the private sector, etc. The AB has the goal to supplement EPOS ON consortium expertise and to provide advice throughout different stages of the EPOS ON development and implementation. The AB it is in charge of:

- overseeing the Project development progress and impact;
- help address the contribution of EPOS ON to innovation-based social growth and related socio-economic impact;
- assessing and monitoring the EPOS ON impact and exploitation.

Advisory Board members are proposed by the OEB and approved by the PC.

2. Representation in meetings

In accordance with the EPOS ON Consortium Agreement “6.2 Operational procedures for all Consortium Bodies”, any Member of a Board:

- should be present or represented at any meeting;
- may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting;
- shall participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

2.1 Convening meetings

The Chair of each board shall convene meetings of that Consortium Body.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
PC	At least once a year	At any time upon written request of the OEB or 1/3 of the members of the PC
OEB	At least quarterly	At any time upon written request of any member of the OEB
NACB	At least once a year	At any time upon written request of any member of the NACB
AB	At least once a year	At any time upon written request of any member of the AB, and by the Chair of the PC following a request approved by the PC itself.

2.2 Notice of a meeting

The Chair of each board shall give written notice of a meeting to each Member of that Consortium Body as soon as possible and no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
PC	30 calendar days	15 calendar days
OEB	14 calendar days	7 calendar days
NACB	30 calendar days	15 calendar days
AB	30 calendar days	20 calendar days

2.3 Sending the agenda

The Chair of each board shall prepare and send each Member of that Consortium Body an agenda no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

PC	21 calendar days, 10 calendar days for extraordinary meetings
OEB	7 calendar days, 7 calendar days for extraordinary meetings
NACB	21 calendar days, 7 calendar days for extraordinary meetings
AB	21 calendar days, 7 calendar days for extraordinary meetings

2.4 Adding agenda items

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the members of a Consortium Body must be identified as such on the agenda.

Any Member of the Board may add an item to the original agenda by written notice to all of the other members of that Consortium Body up to the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

PC	14 calendar days for decision items, 7 calendar days for items for discussion or any agenda items for an extraordinary meeting
OEB	2 working days
NACB	2 working days
AB	2 working days

During a meeting, if all the members of a Consortium Body are present or represented, they can unanimously agree to add a new item to the original agenda.

2.5 Minutes of meetings

The Chair of each board shall produce written minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. The chairperson shall send the draft minutes to all members within 10 calendar days of the meeting.

The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending, no Member has sent an objection in writing to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes.

The Chair shall send the accepted minutes to all the members of the Consortium Body and to the coordinator, who shall retain copies of them.

Minutes of the OEB meetings, once accepted, shall be sent by the coordinator to the PC members for information.

3. Quality Control Procedures

Quality control procedure focuses on ensuring the best quality in preparation of the deliverables, interim, periodic and final reports. The purposes of the quality control procedures are the following:

- make the EPOS ON stakeholders confident in the quality of the work that the project teams are performing, putting in evidence how the project is developed, measured, monitored, accounted and safeguarded during its implementation;
- clearly define the content, format, sign-off and review process, and responsibilities for each deliverable;
- provide the Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB) and the Project Council (PC) with adequate information to organize quality assurance and control activities that include transfer of information, verification actions, etc.;
- provide all the project participants with procedures, rules and applicable methods.

The project coordinator will supervise and guarantee a consistent quality of the EPOS ON outcomes and will be supported by the Optimization and Evolution Board (EB) for dealing both strategic and technical issues and will be responsible for the timely delivery of results on behalf of each beneficiary, assuring the quality of the work executed, monitoring budgetary and technical results.

The Executive Coordination Office (ECO) will provide specific instructions and templates for the reporting.

3.1 Submission of Deliverables

The Lead Beneficiary is responsible for the deliverable production. The Lead Beneficiary is requested to maintain adequate control on the participants' contributions. This duty is extended to all levels of third parties.

The Lead Beneficiary's responsibilities include the following activities:

- assembling and homogenizing inputs from task/WP partners;
- document writing and editing;
- document finalization and revision by the WP leader;

Deliverable documents are edited following a standard format provided by the Executive Coordination Office (ECO). The use of the format-template for deliverables is mandatory.

3.2 Quality of Deliverables

A deliverable review process has been implemented to ensure the high quality of the specific outputs.

The OEB has assigned Reviewer 1 and Reviewer 2 based on the relevance of their expertise to the activities. Table 1 presents the distribution of the deliverable reviews. To ensure impartiality, reviewers are project partners who were not involved in drafting the document. They may or may not be members of the respective Work Package (WP). Due to the nature of specific deliverables related to transversal activities, the

OEB, composed of WP Leaders, will serve as the reviewer for these deliverables. Reviewers are expected to provide constructive written suggestions for improvements to the deliverable's Lead Beneficiary.

Table 2 shows the four steps of the deliverable review process along with its responsible, and the related schedule.

All the EPOS ON deliverables produced during the project's lifespan will be shared with the PC and Service Coordination Committee (SCC).

Table 1 - Deliverable review distribution

EPOS ON Deliverables						
WP No	Div. No	Div. Name	Lead	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Due Date
WP1	D1.1	Management plan and quality procedures	EPOS ERIC	OEB	-	31 Oct 2024
WP1	D1.2	First report on KPIs and risks monitoring	EPOS ERIC	UU	GFZ	31 Oct 2025
WP1	D1.3	Second report on KPIs and risks monitoring	EPOS ERIC	UU	GFZ	30 Jun 2026
WP1	D1.4	Data Management Plan	EPOS ERIC	INGV	UiB	28 Feb 2025
WP1	D1.5	Updated Data Management Plan	EPOS ERIC	INGV	UiB	28 Feb 2026
WP1	D1.6	Dissemination, exploitation, communication Plan	EPOS ERIC	GEM	ZRC SAZU	28 Feb 2025
WP1	D1.7	Updated dissemination, exploitation, communication Plan	EPOS ERIC	ORB	ZRC SAZU	28 Feb 2026
WP1	D1.8	Report on exploitable actions and outcomes	EPOS ERIC	UNINA	ORB	30 Jun 2027
WP1	D1.9	1st Policy Brief	EPOS ERIC	OEB	-	28 Feb 2026
WP1	D1.10	2nd Policy Brief	EPOS ERIC	OEB	-	28 Feb 2026
WP1	D1.11	Final report on dissemination, exploitation, communication activities	EPOS ERIC	ISPRA	ZRC SAZU	31 Aug 2027
WP2	D2.2	Guidelines for new communities integration	GFZ	EUCENTRE	UU	31 Aug 2025
WP2	D2.3	Roadmap for integration of KMT outputs	GFZ	IGF PAS	IMO	28 Feb 2027
WP2	D2.4	Report on ICS-D framework implementation	AGH / AGH-UST	NGI	CNR	28 Feb 2027

WP3	D3.1	Report on products to support risk management	INGV	INCDFFP-RA	GEM	28 Feb 2027
WP3	D3.2	Report on EPOS services for UCPKN	INGV	NOA	EPOS ERIC	28 Feb 2027
WP3	D3.3	Recommendations for consolidation of EPOS Ethical Guidelines	INGV	RBI	LTU	28 Feb 2027
WP3	D3.4	Report on EPOS contribution to environmental impact reduction	ISPRA	INGV	CNR	28 Feb 2027
WP4	D4.1	Activity Plan for user interaction	CNRS	UU	IG PAS	28 Feb 2025
WP4	D4.2	Report on the consolidation of the EPOS User Strategy	CNRS	BRGM	KOERI	28 Feb 2027
WP5	D5.1	Report on MoUs implementation	ORB	IST-ID	AUTH	28 Feb 2027
WP5	D5.2	Roadmap for implementation of international collaboration	IST-ID	INGV	UNINA	28 Feb 2025
WP5	D5.3	Final report on international collaboration	IST-ID	INGV	GFZ	28 Feb 2027
WP5	D5.4	Recommendations for EPOS contribution to EOSC	EPOS ERIC	AGH / AGH-UST	CNRS - UCA	28 Feb 2027
WP6	D6.1	First report on the optimization and evolution of EPOS RI	EPOS ERIC	OEB	-	28 Feb 2026
WP6	D6.2	Final report on the optimization and evolution of EPOS RI	EPOS ERIC	OEB	-	30 Jun 2027
WP6	D6.3	Report on the implementation of the IT tool	EPOS ERIC	CNR	INGV	28 Feb 2027

Table 2 - The four steps of the deliverable review process

Step	Who	What	When
1	Deliverable Lead Beneficiary (DLB)	Shares the deliverable draft to the two reviewers, the WP Leader and the project coordinator (management@epos-eric.eu)	1 month before the deadline for submission
2	Reviewer 1 Reviewer 2	Review the deliverable and provide comments to the Lead Beneficiary.	Within 15 days before the deadline for submission.
3	Deliverable Lead Beneficiary (DLB)	The Lead Beneficiary sends the revised final version of the deliverable to the coordinator (management@epos-eric.eu).	1 week before the deadline for submission.
4	Coordinator	The coordinator submits the final Deliverable to the European Commission.	In respect of the DoA deadline.

The Lead-Beneficiary Contact Person should inform and provide a justification to the WP Leader and the Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB) in case the deliverable is delayed or not made available at the deadline specified. The same applies in case of the reviewers' feedback is ongoing beyond the deadline limit.

3.3 Submission of EC Periodic and Final Reports

Technical Reporting:

- Each WP will produce **six-monthly Internal Reports (IRs)** following the guidelines provided by WP1 and WP6. The Internal Reports will be released in the following months: M6 (February 2025), M11 (July 2025), M17 (January 2026), M22 (June 2026), M27 (November 2026), and M34 (June 2027).
- **Periodic technical reporting** to the European Commission: M18 (February 2026) and M36 (August 2027).

Financial Reporting:

- **Financial interim report:** M9 (May 2025) and M27 (November 2026).
- **Periodic financial reporting to the EC:** M18 (February 2026) and M36 (August 2027).

The coordinator must submit the **Periodic Report** – including both technical and financial report - within **60 days** following the end of each official reporting period and a **Final Report**, including the certificates on financial statements (if applicable). The prompt and accurate submission of periodic and final reports directly affects the distribution of interim and final payments by the EC. The interim report will not be submitted to the EC and will be shared only internally and they will pave the way to the official reporting to the EC. Furthermore, interim reports will help monitoring the beneficiaries'/linked third parties' cash flow.

3.4 Quality of EC Periodic and Final Reports

In view of favouring a smooth and straightforward process, the Executive Coordination Office (ECO) provides specific internal procedures and templates for technical and financial reporting. The use of the format-template for reporting is mandatory.

Table 3 - Steps for Technical Report Quality Assurance and Timely Submission

Step	Responsible	Action	Timeline
1	Coordinator, ECO	Provides specific internal procedures and templates for technical reporting to the WP Leaders	2 months before the submission deadline
3	WP Leader	Assembles contributions, homogenizes inputs from WP partners, and transmits the WP Technical Report to the ECO	Within 30 days from the end of the reporting period or according to the specific ECO schedule
4	Coordinator, ECO	Collates and reviews the technical reports, compiles them into a summary document, and consolidates the document	After receiving the WP Technical Reports from the WP Leaders
5	Coordinator, ECO	Submits the final Deliverable to the European Commission	In accordance with the DoA deadline

Each Beneficiary (and, if applicable, its linked third parties) is responsible to fill in its own **financial reporting** and list of dissemination and communication activities. Each Beneficiary is requested to send complete financial report to the ECO **within 30 days** from the end of the reporting period or accordingly to the specific ECO schedule.

4. Monitoring the EPOS ON Project Performance and Risk Management

4.1 EPOS ON KPIs

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the EPOS ON project are defined by the Work Package (WP) leaders at the start of the project. These KPIs will be monitored every six months, with corrective actions implemented if the results of the executed activities do not meet expectations. The Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB) is responsible for approving the project KPIs and overseeing their monitoring to ensure project goals are being met.

4.2 EPOS ON Risk Register

The risks for the EPOS ON project will be officially validated by the WP leaders at the beginning of the project. The EPOS ON Risks identified at the Description of Action (DoA) level are reported in Table 4.

Table 4 - EPOS ON Risks identified at the Description of Action (DoA) level

Description of risk (indicate level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: Low/Medium/High)	Work package(s) involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Delay in reaching the objectives and in the project timetable. (i): Low; (ii): High	WP1	Careful monitoring tasks progress and early identification of potential risks assessed by the project coordinator and WP1.
Non-acceptable quality of the deliverables. (i): Low; (ii): High	WP1	The project management schema foresees a quality control procedure of deliverables.
Inefficient project governance. (i): Low; (ii): High	WP1	Boards at different project levels are established to strengthen the management structure.
Internal communication is not efficient. (i): Low; (ii): High	WP1	Internal communication tools are set-up (e.g., project intranet; mailing list for WP and Boards); more internal meetings are planned.
Inefficient dissemination of results and communication of the project. (i): Low; (ii): High	WP1	Dissemination and communication activities targeting larger audiences are planned.
Poor participation of EPOS stakeholders in the events. (i): Low; (ii): High	WP1	Use of Social Network channels, engagement activities and further targeted measures are adopted to directly involve EPOS stakeholders.
Lack of suitable exploitable actions. (i): Low; (ii): High	WP1 to WP6	Exploitable actions and outcomes from the project in relation to the target groups monitored yearly.
Turnover of staff at the partner institutions causing poor performance. (i): Low; (ii): High	WP1	Partners inform the coordinator timely and ensure handover of the activities. If a specific issue arises, the partner/s is approached to resolve issues before formal intervention.
Covid-19 pandemic and other external factors affecting travels. (i): Low; (ii): High	WP1 to WP6	Meetings, workshops and events will be organized in hybrid or virtual mode.
Lack of internal coordination for harmonizing the service content among relevant participants. (i) Low; (ii) Medium	WP2	Follow up the service development through regular meetings.
Access to industrial data not compliant with EPOS policy. (i): Low; (ii): Medium	WP2	Clarify data policy with industrial partners early in the project.
Eruption at Krafla site delay deployment of the infrastructure (i): Low; (ii): Medium	WP2	Activities moved to other nearby sites.
Commitment from individual Built Environment Data community is low. (i): Low; (ii): Medium	WP2	Explaining the expected commitment early in the project.
No relevant earthquakes during testing of EEWS software. (i): High; (ii): Medium	WP3	Tests will be also performed with archived waveform data of past large earthquakes and in Near-Fault Observatories with such recordings.
Difficulties in integrating new layers in the ShakeMap platform. (i): Medium; (ii): Low	WP3	Involvement of ShakeMap platform developers in the task, continual communication between all providers.
Licensing or access policy change for the preferred database on environmental impact of building materials (i): Low; (ii): Low	WP3	Use existing alternative databases, which are slightly less complete, but can serve as a backup plan.

Security breaches on the server used to generate the infographics. (i): Low; (ii): Low	WP3	Running the software in redundant systems, with real-time monitoring and institutional firewall to prevent unauthorized access.
ETAS implementation for Euro-Mediterranean Region computationally intensive. (i): Low; (ii): Low/Medium)	WP3	Software optimization and powerful hardware are necessary. If access to large scale computational is not secure, ETH cloud computation will be possible.
Delay in the provision of satellite data and/or temporary unavailability of computational resources. (i): Low; (ii): Low/Medium	WP3	Periodic maintenance of the hardware and upgrades of the software.
EPOS services improvements selected by UCPKN not yet fulfilling the scopes. (i): Low/Medium; (ii): Low/Medium	WP3	The improvements agreed are applied only to a restricted area and/or offline.
Lack of information necessary to process data landscape analysis and environmental impacts. (i): Low; (ii): Medium	WP3	Bilateral interaction will be carried out in order to collect all the information needed.
The information collected is inconsistent for developing impact scenarios (e.g., Urban Geo-climate assessment). (i): Low; (ii): Medium	WP3	Continuous dialogue with WPs ensured, so that once identified inconsistencies are incorporated in the strengthening of the services or in the information for technological evolutions
Failure to hire project staff in a timely manner. (i): Low; (ii): Medium	WP4	Advertise early (before project start), leverage EPOS network for advertising.
Lack of responsiveness from users in interacting & providing information. (i): Medium; (ii): Medium	WP4	Leverage EPOS and scientific peer networks for efficient communication with users.
Failure in the communication and dissemination activities to users. (i): Low; (ii): Medium	WP4	Allowing sufficient for user feedback. Re-orientation of the communication and dissemination strategy.
Lack of engagement of pan-European initiatives. (i): Low; (ii): Medium	WP5	Build on the existing bilateral relations between beneficiaries and European initiatives; focus on initiatives motivated to collaborate with EPOS.
Lack of engagement of international initiatives. (i): Medium; (ii): Medium	WP5	Build on the existing bilateral relations between beneficiaries and international initiatives; focus on initiatives motivated to collaborate with EPOS.
Poor attendance of stakeholders from USA, Australia, Latin America, Africa at meetings. (i): Medium; (ii): Medium	WP5	Allow for hybrid meetings and organize additional virtual meetings.
Poor engagement of EPOS stakeholders participating in EOSC activities. (i): Medium; (ii): Medium	WP5	EPOS stakeholders will be kept actively involved by the SCC in the framework of the EOSC activities.
Ineffective communication with WP leaders. (i): Low; (ii): High	All	Two channels for the interaction with WP leaders: directly between WP6 and each WP; through OEB.
Delay in some activities of the WPs in the project impacting D6.1 and D6.2. (i): Medium; (ii): Medium	All	Close monitoring of project activities at the WP level through regular meetings of OEB.

Reduced interest of countries in attending the NACB. (i): Low; (ii): High	All	Coordination with all WPs to channel information to NACB on their country participation in EPOS.
Ineffective communication with national research organizations. (i): Medium; (ii): High	WP6	Formal approach to interact with key research organizations if the approach endorsed by WP6, OEB and SCC is not working.
Back-office tool not fully implemented by the end of the project. (i): Low; (ii): Medium	WP6	If the risk is increasing, review requirements by M18 and guarantee a completed tool by M33.

The Risk Register will list all foreseeable risks and assess the potential threats to the project's success. The OEB will be responsible for approving the Risk Register and conducting risk monitoring on a six-month basis.

WP leaders will identify risks that may arise at the WP level, taking into account the critical risks for implementation as outlined in the Description of Action (DoA). The Risk Register is considered a living document, continuously updated as the project progresses to reflect new risks or changes to existing ones.

To provide a comprehensive overview of KPI and risk monitoring, the following two deliverables are planned:

- D1.2 First Report on KPIs and Risk Monitoring - EPOS ERIC - M14 (October 2025)
- D1.3 Second Report on KPIs and Risk Monitoring - EPOS ERIC - M22 (June 2026)

These reports are scheduled for M14 and M22 to ensure that key performance metrics and risks are assessed at critical milestones in the project timeline.

5. Internal Communication

EPOS ON's internal communication aims to ensure proper project execution by optimizing the flow of communication between partners, in line with the project's management structure. Establishing efficient internal communication is essential to create a shared understanding of EPOS ON's mission, align efforts to achieve project goals, maintain workflow and timelines, and facilitate coordinated risk management. Effective communication also supports decision-making processes, promotes transparency, and enhances collaboration among all stakeholders.

The main tools that will be used during the project to accomplish the internal communication among the partners are:

5.1 EPOS ON Confluence collaboration tool

Confluence collaboration is planned to be used in the EPOS ON project to centralize project documentation and facilitate communication among team members. It serves as a digital workspace where partners can create, share, and manage content efficiently, ensuring that all stakeholders have access to the latest project information. The platform supports document versioning, feedback integration, and organized knowledge sharing, making it an essential tool for maintaining alignment across the project's workflow and objectives.

5.2 Mailing lists

In order to support cooperation among all beneficiaries, promote transparency, and encourage participation in the decision-making process, several mailing lists have been created by the Coordinating Organization's EPOS ERIC Communication Unit:

Mailing Lists

WP1	wp1-epos-on@lists.epos-eu.org
WP2	wp2-epos-on@lists.epos-eu.org
WP3	wp3-epos-on@lists.epos-eu.org
WP4	wp4-epos-on@lists.epos-eu.org
WP5	wp5-epos-on@lists.epos-eu.org
WP6	wp6-epos-on@lists.epos-eu.org
Project Council (PC)	pc-epos-on@lists.epos-eu.org
Optimization and Evolution Board (OEB)	oeb-epos-on@lists.epos-eu.org
OEB + SCC (for WP1 and WP6 purpose)	oeb-scc-epos-on@lists.epos-eu.org
National Authorities Consultation Board (NACB)	nacb-epos-on@lists.epos-eu.org
Advisory Board (AB)	ab-epos-on@lists.epos-eu.org

The contact list has been populated by WP Leaders and PC members. For any changes to the contacts (e.g., WP members), an email must be sent to management@epos-eric.eu.

The lists, along with all the project documentation, will be available on the Confluence collaboration tool, provided specifically for the EPOS ON Project.

5.3 Meetings

Regular meetings (in-person or virtual) will ensure proper interaction, facilitate the exchange of key results, and allow for monitoring the performance, effectiveness, and relevance of executed activities. In particular,

- PC meetings, organized yearly (in-person) in the framework of the EPOS Days (see Task 1.4), to ensure good project implementation. An additional PC meeting will be organized at the end of the project.
- OEB meetings, organized quarterly (of which 2 per year in-person) to monitor project activities and results, proposing corrective actions if needed. The OEB will also have the key role of meeting the SCC once a year.
- AB meetings, organized yearly (in person). Additional face-to-face meetings, virtual or hybrid meetings might be organized if needed.
- Regular in person meetings and/or teleconferences with the involved beneficiaries will be organized at WP level to gain smooth communication on activities at the task level.

The EPOS ON project Kick-off Meeting was held in Rome on October 2nd and 3rd in a hybrid format, enabling strong in-person attendance while also allowing participation from those unable to attend physically.

6. Conclusion

This Management and Quality Control Plan sets out the procedures and standards to be followed throughout the project, as well as the responsibilities for ensuring adherence to these procedures and standards.

The plan remains effective throughout the project's lifecycle but is adaptable to revisions if required. The responsibilities for quality planning, assurance, and control are shared among all partners, enabling diverse perspectives on quality issues to achieve the best possible outcomes.